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“WHY RESISTORS MATTER IN ELECTRONICS”

Electronic devices are everywhere, from small toys and entertainment gadgets to communication and industrial devices, which are commonly understood and easy to define. But talking about electronic circuits is more difficult; only electronics students and related professionals understand their connections. Among those components forming a functional circuit is a resistor.

The resistor is a small, color-coded, cylindrical shape, some types with a printed numerical value rectangle in shape, that introduces electrical resistance in the circuit, and it is considered a basic electronic device, part of every complex electronic circuit that helps to regulate voltage and current flow that protects other working devices, such as light-emitting diodes (LEDs) and transistors, to set their required parameters to work properly in the circuit, providing a meaningful operation and function according to its design. Besides being small, resistors contribute significantly to every electronic circuit.

Student encounters with resistors usually occur in the classroom through the study of electronic circuit diagrams and in the study of Ohm's Law that calculates the difference between resistance, voltage, and current in the circuit. The concept seems abstract theoretically, but practical hands-on experience brings the reality that understanding penetrates every learner when they religiously focus on their study. Practical experience dealing with resistors begins during the construction of electronic circuits in the laboratory; they witness how resistors limit current, divide voltage, and prevent damage to other sensitive components in the circuit. The absence or incorrect value of a resistor often results in circuit failure by damaging other components or by causing erratic behavior of the circuit.

The resistor matters in electronics because it is the fundamental device introducing electrical resistance that helps the success of a complicated electronic circuit purposely designed to contribute functional and useful operation in every practical application from the smallest to the largest system in electronics adaptively in the advancement of technology, especially in the entertainment, communication, and control systems.

